

Simulation Model Tracking System: a Digital Twin-based technology to improve the thermal performance of Data Centres

Sergio Velásquez Correa
R+D Department
IDP Ingegneria, a Bureau Veritas
Company
Barcelona, Spain
ORCID: 0000-0002-4658-1854

Rossano Scoccia
Buildings' environment and energy
systems Research Group
Politecnico di Milano
Milano, Italy
ORCID: 0000-0002-4658-1854

Marcello Aprile
Sistemi energetici e ambientali negli
edifici Research Group
Politecnico di Milano
Milano, Italy
ORCID: 0000-0003-0233-7021

Pablo Vicente-Legazpi
R+D Department
Building Digital Twin Association
(BDTA)
Antwerpen, Belgium
ORCID: 0009-0009-2231-1647

Eduard Loscos Domingo
R+D Department
Building Digital Twin Association
(BDTA)
Antwerpen, Belgium
ORCID: 0009-0009-8351-1503

Abstract— The versatility of digital twins (DTws), especially when complemented by predictive and real-time simulation models, allows for their full potential in the design or validation of dynamic and coordinated environments such as data centres, where architectural components, installed IT systems, and climate control systems coexist to create a functional and thermally stable system of systems. By seamlessly connecting physical systems with their digital counterparts in real time, these technologies enable continuous and synchronized simulation with monitoring systems, as well as dynamic control of energy consumption. This article proposes the fusion of a simulation model with model predictive control (MPC) to establish adaptive and fault-tolerant energy strategies, specifically for data centres (DCs), running from a digital twin platform. Using simulation tools standards as SIMBOTs, a term conceived within the framework of the European project SPHERE [1], funded by the European Commission, the aim is to model virtual performance under precise thermal conditions, encompassing cooling systems at both the building level and in the racks. Therefore, a novel synthetic solution is presented and designed to optimize energy use and facilitate waste heat recovery within the framework of a “Building Digital Twin Environment” as a “Platform as a Service” of the DC at the University Politecnico di Milano in Bovisa - Italy. This platform provides comprehensive visualization and real-time operational monitoring of the data centre, facilitating decision-making to adjust critical parameters and comparatively improve its thermal performance. Furthermore, the aim is to demonstrate how thermal simulations for data centres and high-performance computing (HPC) assets enable HVAC professionals to implement sustainable cooling strategies, ensuring accurate energy resource accounting, adherence to recognized standards, and strict compliance with environmental regulations.

Keywords— *Digital Twin, Data Centre, Waste Heat Recovery, Energy Efficiency, ECM, Heat pump, SMTS, BDTE, PaaS, SIMBOT, MPC, SIL*

I. INTRODUCTION (HIGHLIGHTS IN DATA CENTRE COOLING)

Data centre cooling is undergoing rapid transformation as operators confront rising thermal loads, sustainability regulations, and cost pressures. Emerging trends include accelerated adoption of liquid cooling, heat reuse, and

analytics-driven optimization to manage higher temperatures and reduce environmental impact. These developments reflect a broader shift toward integrated, data-informed cooling strategies designed to improve efficiency and resilience at scale [2]. By the other hand, explosive growth in AI workloads is pushing rack power densities to unprecedented levels, undermining traditional assumptions about thermal inertia and response times. Industry experts report GPU racks drawing up to 132 kW to-day, with designs targeting 1 MW and beyond — conditions where cooling continuity becomes mission critical and cannot wait for backup generation to ramp up. Meanwhile, operators face acute power capacity constraints in major hubs, compounding the urgency to optimize cooling as part of a holistic energy strategy [3]. Despite initiatives to capture and reuse waste heat, though adoption varies and isn't advancing uniformly across facilities.

AI- and IoT-enabled controls, phase-change materials, and smart orchestration are gaining traction to deliver dynamic, workload-aware cooling that adjusts to real-time conditions. Collectively, these innovations signal a move toward more modular, intelligent, and sustainable cooling architectures. Besides innovation, many operators report gaps: 34% say current cooling solutions are inadequate, and 21% are actively seeking better approaches, underscoring the scale of the optimization challenge. Cooling is increasingly seen as inseparable from power protection, with UPS strategies evolving to ensure continuous cooling during grid disturbances and transitional power events. This convergence positions cooling as a competitive differentiator, influencing design choices and service-level commitments [5].

The proposed Simulation Model Tracking System (STMS), built within a Digital Twin environment, integrates AI-driven predictive control, real-time simulation capabilities, and direct links to facility energy systems to support increasingly stringent environmental requirements. As these technologies evolve and industry practices mature, cooling will become an intelligent, adaptive layer within the data centre—optimizing performance, resilience, and sustainability. Operators who align their cooling strategies with workload characteristics, power constraints, and heat-reuse opportunities will be best pre-pared to meet the

challenges of 2027, when the HyCool-IT project concludes, and to continue advancing beyond it.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK & ARCHITECTURE OF BDTE

The HyCool-IT project's digital twin environment focuses on an optimizing energy consumption model for the cooling system at POLIMI. It is based on the standard architecture defined by ISO 23247-2 and the ISO 19650 series standards (Organization and digitization of information about building and civil engineering works, including BIM). This architecture is designed to facilitate seamless integration and real-time interaction between physical and digital devices, enhancing the efficiency of the POLIMI server room.

A. Multi-Layered Architecture

The architecture consists of the following sections:

- physical (architecture envelope – Server room),
- MEP, sensors and control systems - data centre components – controlled objects,
- Monitored data,
- digital services (Optimized Simulation – SIMBOTS and Model Predictive Control – MPC), and
- the integration ecosystem called the simulation tracking model system – SMTS

Fig. 1. HyCool-IT Digital Twin Environment Architecture. (Own elaboration)

The physical elements are listed and inventoried including the main components of the cooling system, they are connected through the instrumentation that is also inventoried, the physical assets are connected through protocols in the communication and control units in a so-called connection layer. The digital twin environment in the digital layer drives services in a services layer, enabling launching the energy consumption model based on SIMBOTS (Simulation Bots) of the cooling system and the model predictive control (MPC) that make possible to analyse critical deviations from actual thermal behaviour and the optimal one estimated.

The digital twin data model manages and integrates all the data generated by the monitoring, control, simulation and predictive components in two categories, internal and external services based on software solutions and algorithms, these services present a holistic architecture platform to support the decision processes to reach an optimal energy consumption model (ECM), based on a sustainable thermal performance model (TPM) together with other services of digital twins like maintenance and performance monitoring. This layered architecture follows the principle of separation of concerns, allowing for high modularity and reusability, which improves

scalability and reduces the developmental complexity of the digital twin. Detailed information about the architecture will be provided in the following subsections.

B. Creating the BDTE

The Building Digital Twin Environment (BDTE) is being implemented in the way of a Platform as a Service (PaaS) with specific Web API communication microservices. These microservices will connect various tools to support planning and design assessment, commissioning, and performance evaluation processes, including advanced technical equipment solutions digitalized as asset digital twin instance (ADTWI) [6] SIMBOTS (interactive simulators) within an ICT Ecosystem. This enables a more effective integration of operation/performance monitoring as an advanced server room or intelligent building management system.

III. DIGITAL TWIN INTEGRATION: FROM PHYSICS TO DIGITAL SERVICES

To achieve interoperability, a BIM-to-Simulation resource is required to map IFC entities into the corresponding simulation elements and vice versa.

These resources ensure that:

- Spaces in BIM (IFCSpaces) become thermal or airflow volumes in the simulation.
- Subspaces (e.g. cold aisle, hot aisle, underfloor plenum) are generated automatically from BIM geometry.
- Equipment elements (e.g. racks, InRow units, CDUs, chillers) become integrated SIMBOTS or final SIMBOTS depending on data availability.
- Piping systems (IFCPipeSegment, IFCPipeFitting, IFCPump, IFCValve) are translated into hydronic networks in the simulation environment.

A BIM-Simulation Interface would define the rules, identifiers and geometric constraints used to automatically transform a BIM model (IFC) into a ready-to-simulate SIMBOT environment. This would ensure consistency between the digital twin, the simulation layer and the operational monitoring systems. But there is an intrinsic inconsistency in this approach. Initial BIM spaces may be too large to be used in simulation. And the opposite occurs with piping systems, which are represented in simulation with less detail. In the case of the Hycool-IT Project, the integration between BIM and simulation was initially proposed aimed at a common semantic knowledge base, using the BOT ontology to move from BIM to a topology more assimilable by simulation models, and OPCUA to integrate the simulation results with the BOT result. In the ICT integration, the use of an external database (InfluxDB) was also proposed as a solution.

The line registration protocol allows several tags to be assigned to the same data in real time, so it was seen as a possible solution to gather measurement data, simulation results and any reference element to represent in the BIM model. However, the solution finally taken has been the integration of all the results into the 3D viewer of the IDP DTw platform. The real-time simulation results are sent with an OPCUA protocol and are integrated into the DTw Platform. While commands and inputs for the simulation are sent from

the same interface to the simulation deck in OPCUA. Therefore, the BIM integration has been carried out in the Real-Time Platform, restricted to monitoring signals, simulation results and BIM models.

A. Physical Process Simulation

a SIMBOT is a digital twin component (or DTwC) [5], with the mathematical representation of a market model. SIMBOTs must replicate the functionality of equipment's and building components, to make possible to implement a simulation model in an economic time.

SIM-BOTs are real-time oriented, and its representation must be adapted to quick integration times and sampling rates of 5-15 min, which are typical of supervision tasks in buildings. Together with basic components of several disciplines, a complete simulation model of the data centre is possible. The final simulation run time model can be applied for design, commissioning or exploitation phases, making it quite reliable and potentially interesting as a new investment.

B. Real-Time Monitoring

In the monitoring service, real-time data generated at the physical layer is captured by the perception unit within the connection layer and transmitted to the data unit in the digital layer for storage and processing in the digital twin environment. This data is then forwarded to the model unit, where the monitoring model is activated. Both the incoming data and the model's output commands are stored and visualized. If an anomaly is detected, an alert notification is displayed to the operator.

Fig. 2. Inrow cooler Z3-IR-C1 inventoried in the Digital Twin platform and connected to the monitoring system at POLIMI. (Own elaboration)

C. Model Predictive Control

To enable the automatic control of an HVAC system, a low-level control algorithm is essential. For smart and advanced control within HYCOOL-IT, Model Predictive Control (MPC) was chosen to regulate the cooling system presented in Figure 4. The MPC service consists of a system model and an optimization engine, which together generate the optimal control strategy to maintain server room temperature, as illustrated in Figure 2. MPC leverages the system model to determine the best control actions over a predefined time horizon.

The primary inputs to this service are real-time HVAC system measurements, which help assess the current system state and optimize future control actions.

Fig. 3. Digital Twin Environment (geometrical model and services integration), showing the racks (geometrical model and services integration), showing the racks and rack in coolers inventory. (a) HOT aisle containment (b) COLD aisle [4] (Own elaboration)

The service is being developed in Python, making deployment straightforward using Docker. Docker simplifies deployment by packaging the application and its dependencies into a lightweight, portable container, ensuring consistency across different environments.

The MPC service's Docker container will be deployed on the IMP Linux server, while real-time system measurements, which serve as key inputs, will be hosted at POLIMI. To facilitate data access, the hosting service's IP address will be authorized for data retrieval from the POLIMI system. Beyond real-time measurements, there is potential to incorporate outputs from other services. However, at the time of writing this report, these integrations have not yet been implemented in the MPC service. The outputs of the MPC will be transmitted to the POLIMI platform via Digital Twin.

Fig. 4. MPC service schema (Own elaboration)

D. SMTS

The SMTS optimization process involves minimizing the difference between the slopes of the HVAC power consumption curve and the cooling generation curve estimated from the waste heat available and the sorption chiller cooling capacity. In addition, the deviations associated with room-temperature optimization must be considered. This allows to obtain optimal control variables within a finite time horizon. Optimal control sequence in the server room must be used as the output parameter for the control. The optimized parameters for the DCUs, HVAC systems, and indoor thermal environment must be updated with the new parameters provided by the MPC. The system then outputs the final actual cooling capacity, which is compared with the value predicted by the prediction model.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION: DATA CENTRE - POLIMI CASE STUDY

Within HYCOOL-IT project, MPC is envisioned for server room temperature control. As explained in detail in deliverable 1.2 "Bovisa Campus Pilot audit and KPI definitions", IT infrastructure is in Z3 room in the Bovisa campus in POLIMI, and the corresponding 3D layout in Figure 5. The main heat generators in the room are 4 rows of server racks, which are separated in two-by-two configuration

of hot-aisle containments (HAC). Therefore, servers are taking cold air from outside the HAC and are releasing the heat within the HAC in the hot corridor between the server rows by using InRow coolers, returning the cooled air to the outside (cold side).

Fig. 5. Z3 3D layout. (Own elaboration)

When the external cooling system is considered, it consists of two water chillers, two cooling distribution units (CDUs), for evenly distributing cold water through the system and twelve InRow coolers in line with the racks, as given in Figure 5. The InRow coolers are taking the hot air from the HAC aisle, cooling it using the cold water and exhausting it on the other side in the cold aisle, as it can be noticed by analysing the temperatures from the previously mentioned figure. With the purpose of understanding the control variables and the controlled variables, in Figure 6, schematic representation of the cooling system is given for one InRow unit.

All other InRow coolers are designed in the same way. In black text in the figure, air-related variables are given, while water-related variables are denoted in blue and control variables are marked in red. However, only the ones that are circled are available in the POLIMI monitoring system. Hence, it could be concluded that, by adjusting valve position and fan speed, room temperature, as the primary variable of concern, could be subjected to control.

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of cooling system components. (Own elaboration)

A. SIMBOTS Environment

SIMBOTS are defined and developed in HyCool-IT Deliverable “D1.3 Methodological guidelines including SIMBots creation and framework for Software in the loop (SiL) implementation”. Within this guideline, one SIMBot is used as an equipment component. The InRow Cooler SIMBOT has been created following the schematic below. From the left, we have modelled a single ventilator. There is a total amount of air ventilated of about 1980 l/sec. They have variable speed and can be working at 60-70-80-90-100%. The input power of the unit is 1900W, with 15A (230V). We will add an electrical motor to the ventilator.

Fig. 7. InRow Cooler SIMBOT model. (Own elaboration from ECOSIMPRO software)

The schematic in Figure 7 can be reduced to a symbol with no parameters to be inserted in a new model, as we can see below:

Fig. 8. InRow Cooler SIMBOT definition. (Own elaboration from ECOSIMPRO software)

The heat exchanger is working with a maximum water flow of 6.3 l/s (bypass valve closed). If we define a target temperature difference of 15°C, then we can calculate the maximum heat flow in the heat exchanger (we have the air flow and the temperature difference to get). And the same for the water flow. So, with the maximum air ventilated and maximum water flow, and the temperature difference we can get the (approx.) dimensions of the heat exchanger.

Some of the problems we are facing are the instability of water circuits, with peaks of pressure and problems with mathematical convergence. The heat exchanger may be too complicated to use the library supplied by the developer. So, a simpler approach could be used instead. The 3-way valve needs a control implementation, and the fan as well. This control algorithm is unknown, and a simple control will be implemented.

For testing the IRCooler model we are working is a model like this below:

Fig. 9. InRow Cooler SIMBOT tested. (Own elaboration from ECOSIMPRO software)

As we can see, there are 4x rack SIMBOTs (generic SIMBOT, parametric) and one InRow Cooler (Component A1). The water circuit is simulated with an accumulator to avoid numerical problems. The InRow Cooler component will be connected with the spaces defined in the hot/cold aisles and the water circuit (CDUs), 2 ports for air and 2 port for the cold water.

Regulation of the InRow coolers can be interactive, changing the set point values of temperature. (and hence, temperature difference). Fan control can be used for regulating pressure in the aisles. Once validated, the components of IR Coolers will be integrated in the room, connected with all spaces and racks. The interface of the simulation could be providing similar outputs of those used today in the Ecostruxure interface. Those outputs are communicated using OPCUA protocol, and the simulation can be hosted locally in any computer running windows.

V. TESTING THE SMTS WITH HISTORICAL DATA

To develop a reference framework for SMTS, and with a future standard in mind, a series of tests have been developed with historical data from POLIMI's Z3 data centre. For the development of the tests, node-network (<https://nodered.org/>) has been used as a resource to read monitored and simulated data and to be able to prepare a test platform for SMTS algorithms.

The parameters used are as follows:

A. Variables from historical data (CSV – actual measurements)

- Unit intake air temperature (“Temperatura aria aspirata dall’unità”)
- Unit supply air temperature (“Temperatura aria di mandata dell’unità”)

B. Variables from the simulation deck (simulated signals via OPC-UA)

- Simulation time (externally synchronized)
- InRow Cooler fan speed (IRC Fan)
- Chiller cooling capacity
- Bypass valve opening degree
- Cold aisle temperature

- Hot aisle temperature
- Direct circuit fluid flow rate
- Bypass circuit fluid flow rate

C. Comparable variables and residual calculation

The simulated temperatures of the model (cold aisle and hot aisle) are associated with the historical intake and supply air variables to validate the thermal behaviour.

Based on this correspondence, the instantaneous residuals between the simulated signal and the historical signal are calculated, defined as:

- Residual = Simulated signal – Historical signal

Table I shows a sample of the historical data collected from the sensors of POLIMI's Z3 data centre chiller.

TABLE I. HISTORICAL DATA TAKEN FROM MONITORING SYSTEM AT POLIMI DATA CENTRE USED FOR THE SIMULATION

Dispositivo	Sensore	Ora	Valore	UnitÀ
Z3-Chiller1	Temperatura ingresso acqua	01/06/2024 00:00	13	Å° C
Z3-Chiller1	Temperatura ingresso acqua	01/06/2024 00:01	13	Å° C
Z3-Chiller1	Temperatura ingresso acqua	01/06/2024 00:04	13.6	Å° C
Z3-Chiller1	Temperatura ingresso acqua	01/06/2024 00:07	14.2	Å° C
Z3-Chiller1	Temperatura ingresso acqua	01/06/2024 00:10	14.5	Å° C
Z3-Chiller1	Temperatura ingresso acqua	01/06/2024 00:13	14.2	Å° C
Z3-Chiller1	Temperatura ingresso acqua	01/06/2024 00:16	13.3	Å° C
Z3-Chiller1	Temperatura ingresso acqua	01/06/2024 00:19	12.4	Å° C
Z3-Chiller1	Temperatura ingresso acqua	01/06/2024 00:22	13	Å° C
Z3-Chiller1	Temperatura ingresso acqua	01/06/2024 00:25	13.6	Å° C

The monitoring data consists of a sampling every 3 min of a multitude of variables from the data centre, from which those corresponding to an InRow Cooler have been extracted. From the historical data compiled from 6 months of operation, the historical data of individual signals have been extracted, and then they have been grouped into “messages” (groups of signals in a json file) that correspond with equipment and each sampling step. With the extraction of these sampled data, a simulated real-time execution has been reproduced, preparing a supervision interface for this purpose.

Fig. 10. Node-red interface for run-time execution. (Own elaboration)

The simulation inputs and outputs have also been managed in node-red, using an OPCUA protocol. In addition to the real-time simulation, the values that feed the simulation inputs and the output results obtained are integrated into the same platform as the sampling visualization.

Fig. 11. Simulation results for cold and hot isles with the temperature behaviour of the inrow cooler unit and the residues between both cold and hot areas (*Own elaboration*)

Subsequently, the values that are going to participate in the SMTS are grouped, each following a specific supervision criterion. Preparing this accessible platform is crucial to develop SMTS algorithms by other technicians, which start from the presentation of SMTS variables in the same environment.

Fig. 12. Simulation results for cold and hot isles with the temperature behaviour of the inrow cooler air input and air output including residuals (*Own elaboration*)

SMTS algorithms can follow a variety of monitoring criteria, from simple residual or delay-compensated residual calculation to more complex calculations using kriging, statistics, and multiple simultaneous parameters.

VI. PRELIMINARY RESULTS & DISCUSSION

This paper summarizes the preliminary architecture of a Simulation Model Tracking System (SMTS) for sustainable re-use of waste heat produced by the server room at POLIMI-Bovisa. The proposed architecture leverages an integrated solution that employs the HyCool-IT Digital Twin to monitor and optimally operate the server room by deploying electrical SCADA control and human machine interfaces based on simulation and prediction models.

The simulations based on SIMBOTS, a novel concept that simplifies complex data structures and physical components architectures, can provide different performance scenarios that may improve control strategies including predicted events and scenarios to diagnose, analyse and improve the performance and reduce uncertainty for malfunctions,

failures, anomalies or defects in physical components. Once created the deck for real-time, an “.exe” file is generated together with some other dll’s. Running the exe file produces the deck to begin the simulation. That simulation has some input/outputs and some extra commands, which may be used to pause the simulation or change some global options. From a Node-red simple program and interface we can be sending INPUTs and commands and can receive outputs. An example of Node-red simple interface for the in-row cooler simulated.

Fig. 13. Node-red interface for run-time execution whole control panel. (*Own elaboration*)

Regarding MPC, following model development, an optimization engine was implemented. A genetic algorithm was used as the core of the optimization part of the MPC. The key hyperparameters were set to 500 generations and 20 solutions per population. The results demonstrate that the developed ML-based models are accurate and reliable enough to support MPC implementation in a real-world server room environment. The selected genetic algorithm showed promising performance, achieving fast convergence in typical scenarios and maintaining robustness even in more complex cases. These findings validate the feasibility of using this MPC framework for temperature control in POLIMI data centre, offering the potential for energy-efficient and responsive cooling strategies.

The SMTS offers significant advantages over a traditional digital-twin environment by enabling comprehensive data analysis, advanced simulation capabilities, and detailed emulation of responses across multiple active devices. It supports the evaluation of protection and control actions by accessing real-time data on demand, retrieving historical data for system assessments, and running one-click simulations to visualize and analyse both initial and post-disturbance system behaviour.

Its intelligent, interactive graphical interface enhances usability by providing simulation alerts, enabling automated

scenario generation through a project wizard, and ensuring precise analyses based on actual operating values.

The situational intelligence applied will simulate and predict responses before aleatory operator's actions based on adaptative performance scenarios. The SMTS applied to the server room power performance and the thermal behaviour is intended to cover specific services implemented in the Building Digital Twin Environment, covering operations and maintenance, planning the changes/variations in the electrical transformers load/overload and cooling load by providing hybrid cooling capacity based on the demand, and switching sequences to reach transient stability. The architecture proposed on this paper will be developed, applied, and validated during the progress of demonstrative work packages of HyCool-IT project, alpha and beta testing tasks during 2026.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors are part of the European HyCool-IT (HYbrid COOLing & management for IT infrastructures) project funded by the European Commission under Grant agreement ID: 101138623.

REFERENCES

- [1] European Horizon 2020 Project SPHERE - Service Platform to Host and Share REsidential data - Project has funded by the European Union's H2020 programme under Grant Agreement No. 820805. <https://sphere-project.eu/>
- [2] Data Centre Knowledge Resource Library. Data Centre Cooling: Trends and Strategies to Watch in 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.datacentreknowledge.com/cooling/data-centre-cooling-trends-and-strategies-to-watch-in-2025>.
- [3] 5 Critical Data Centre Trends Reshaping the Industry in 2025. Align - Data Centre Infrastructure Solutions. [Online]. Available: <https://www.align.com/leadership>
- [4] Trend Report: How data centre cooling challenges are driving UPS innovations. Data Centre Review. [Online]. Available: <https://datacentrereview.com/2025/09/trend-report-how-data-centre-cooling-challenges-are-driving-ups-innovations/>
- [5] Definition taken from the new standard EN 18162:2026 that will be published this 25th FEB2026.
- [6] J M. Takahashi, T. Uekusa, M. Kishita, H. Kaneko, Aisle-capping method for airflow design in data centres, in: Proceedings of the International Telecommunications Energy Conference (INTELEC) (2008), San Diego, CA, September 14–18, 2008.
- [7]] HyCool-IT D1.2 Bovisa Campus Pilot audit and KPI definitions - 2025
- [8] HyCool-IT D1.3 Methodological guidelines including SIMBots creation and framework for Software in the loop (SiL) implementation - 2025
- [9] HyCool-IT D2.2 BDTE Architecture Design - 2025
- [10] HyCool-IT D2.3 SMTS as DTwin Tool - 2025